

Open - Source Library of Parametric Mono-material Scaffolds for Cultivated Meat

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2024

This library's purpose is to present different types of parametric scaffolds to aid research in the cellular agriculture and cultivated protein fields. This prototype aims to act as a library of lattices and scaffolding structures, which could be used for investigative and development purposes.

All scaffolds were designed in Rhino 7 + Grasshopper.
Plug-Ins: Crystallon, Intralattica, Pufferfish, Wombat, Lunchbox,
Axolotl, Weaverbird, Millepede.

To access Rhino and Grasshopper files click [here](#)

How-To Use:

There are 3 columns with different information about the Scaffolds:

<i>Geometry</i>	<i>Images</i>	<i>Applicable Technology</i>
Name		Optimal, *Suboptimal, **Avoid

Example:

<i>Geometry</i>	<i>Images</i>	<i>Applicable Technology</i>
BC CUBIC		MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

Beam Lattices	Images	Applicable Technology
BC		<p>SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**</p>
BC CUBIC		<p>SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**</p>

BC STAR TET

FDM, bioprinting, inkjet printing, SLA, MSLA* DLP*, LCM*, LMM*, SLS, SLM*, 2PP**

DODECAHEDRON

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

EDGE OCTA

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

FC CUBIC

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

NACL

FDM, bioprinting, inkjet printing, SLA, MSLA* DLP*, LCM*, LMM*, SLS, SLM*, 2PP**

OCTA TET

FDM, bioprinting, inkjet printing, SLA, MSLA* DLP*, LCM*, LMM*, SLS, SLM*, 2PP**

PRIM CUBIC

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

STAR TET

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

TETRAHEDRAL

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

TRUNC OCTA

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

VERTEX OCTA

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

**Voronoi
Lattices**

Images

Applicable Technology

VORONOI

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

VORONOI

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing, SLS*, SLS*,
SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

VORONOI

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

TPMS Lattices	Images	Applicable Technology
DIAMOND		SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**
DOUBLE GYROID		SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

FISCHERKOCH

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

FRP

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

GYROID

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

IWP

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

KP

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

LIDINOID

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

NEOVIOUS

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM, inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*, FDM**, bioprinting**

OCTO

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

SCHWARTZP

SLA, MSLA, DLP, 2PP, LCM, LMM,
inkjet printing*, SLS*, SLM*,
FDM**, bioprinting**

Applicable Technology Abbreviations

FDM - fused deposition modeling

MSLA - masked laser stereolithography

SLA - laser stereolithography

DLP - digital light processing

LCM - lithography based ceramic manufacture

LMM - lithography based metal manufacture

SLS - selective laser sintering

SLM (PBLF) - selective laser melting / (powder bed laser fusion)

2PP - two photon polymerization

